

NERC Innovation Project: Decision support for restoring ecological networks in rapidly developing, biodiverse countries

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REPORT ON CASE STUDY: Connectivity in the Cocoa Landscapes of the Krokosua Hills, Western Ghana

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Authored by Lydia Cole¹, Jenny Hodgson¹, Katherine Allen¹, John Heap¹, Winston Asante², Roselyn Fosuah Adjei³, Thomas Gyambrah³, Catherine Parr⁴, Jane Hill⁵ and David Hughell⁴.

¹Department of Evolution, Ecology and Behaviour, University of Liverpool, UK

²Department of Silviculture and Forest Management, Kwame Nrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana

³Climate Change Unit (National REDD+ Secretariat), Forestry Commission of Ghana, Ghana

⁴School of Environmental Sciences, University of Liverpool, UK

⁵Department of Biology, University of York, UK

⁶Rainforest Alliance, UK

A sun cocoa farm in the Krokosua Hills landscape, Western Ghana. (Photo credit to L.Cole, April 2018.)

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I. Introduction to the Project

Condatis is a modelling program for use in landscape planning. It was developed by Dr Jenny Hodgson, based at the University of Liverpool, over five years ago, in response to an evident need to better understand the implications of climate change on biodiversity, and how we might mitigate any negative impacts.

Specifically, Condatis was developed to deal with the dual challenges of habitat fragmentation and climate change. These phenomena are causing there to be a reduced amount and connectedness of habitat, which in turn, makes it more difficult for populations to shift to track changes in temperature. UK conservation organisations concerned with supporting species' survival under ongoing changing environmental conditions, such as [Buglife](#), were looking for a tool to assist them in planning restoration projects that would be effective in connecting up habitats for different target species on a landscape scale. In addition, there is increasing pressure at the global scale, from international environmental policies such as the [New York Declaration on Forests](#), the [Bonn Challenge](#), the [Paris Climate Agreement](#), and the [Sustainable Development Goals](#), to restore forest habitat for the purposes of climate change mitigation through enhanced carbon storage, the conservation of biodiversity and the achievement of sustainable and equitable development.

Condatis was developed to address landscape planning challenges both local to the UK and experienced across the world.

A variety of UK conservation organisations were involved in the testing of the tool during its early development and have been involved in ongoing feedback exercises and subsequent advancements. These relationships were predominantly built as part of a NERC-funded Knowledge Exchange Fellowship, led by Dr Katherine Allen. This ongoing project involves working with stakeholders to introduce them to and support their use of Condatis, and strategic landscape planning in general. Various organisations are now using Condatis to guide landscape management, including [Natural England](#) and [Natural Resources Wales](#).

However, the Condatis Network has not been promoted or used within a developing world, tropical context, where ecological and socio-economic conditions can be quite different. This report forms one of the pieces summarising the activities and outputs of the NERC-funded Innovation project entitled: *Decision support for restoring ecological networks in rapidly developing, biodiverse countries*, which ran from November 2017 until April 2019. The main aim of the project was *to facilitate sustainable land-use planning for tropical developing countries under climate change*, with the following goals:

- i. Create new, accessible **decision support methods**;
- ii. Demonstrate how conservation decisions can be supported in our partner organisations through **three collaborative case studies**; and,
- iii. Create a **freely available web application** for our decision support tool and ensure its long-term accessibility, especially for users in developing countries.

Goals (i) and (iii) have been achieved through the development and launch of Condatis Version 1.0, which can be accessed from any computer, for free, via www.webapp.condatis.org.uk. Each of the three collaborative case studies has focused on advancing a particular component of Condatis:

- 1) *Enhancing Sabah's Protected Area network*, Malaysian Borneo, focused on the prioritisation of habitat cells for connectivity in multiple directions;
- 2) *Scenarios for wildlife corridor restoration in Java*, Indonesia, focused on the inclusion of habitat quality effects for flagship species; and,
- 3) *Expanding shade cocoa in Western Ghana*, focused on robustness to uncertainty when limited ecological data are available.

This report expands on the third case study, exploring the use of Condatis maps in the extension of cocoa agroforestry in the Krokosua Hills landscape, Western Ghana.

II. Introduction to the Case Study: Krokosua Hills landscape in Ghana

Ghana is a diverse country, in terms of ecosystems, spanning coastal planes, seasonal savannah to hill forest, and land uses, from maize, to mining, to oil palm agriculture. One of the country's most important industries is cocoa farming, for use in the production of chocolate. Ghana produces approximately 800,000 tonnes of cocoa beans per year, predominantly from smallholder farms covering some 1.6m ha of the country. With increasing population pressure, a growing global cocoa market to satisfy, all coupled with the ongoing drive for economic development, there is a push for intensification of cocoa production, enabling higher yields from smaller areas of land. If this intensification is to be realised, without requiring smallholder farmers to increase the expending of their limited resources on external inputs, agroforestry must be offered as the alternative. Having

shade trees within the agricultural matrix, at as low a density as 10 to 15 trees per hectare, is shown to have significant results on reducing damage from insect pests, one of the major threats to sustainable cocoa production (Wessel & Quist-Wessel, 2015). Though agroforestry makes sense, from a pest control, nutrient management and longevity of production stand-point, the levels of uptake on the ground are quite different, with technological fixes and the government-incentivised adoption of high-yielding varieties being the common approach adopted (Ruf, 2011).

In recent years, the conservation community has placed an increasing focus on the importance of producing cocoa in a manner that satisfies three key goals: (i) forest protection and restoration, (ii) sustainable cocoa production, and (iii) farmer livelihoods (IDH, 2018). One way of satisfying these requirements is through growing cocoa in mixed agroforestry systems, also known as *shade-grown* or *shade cocoa* (the latter will be used in this report). This system provides small holders with a variety of products from their land, and as a consequence, income streams, offering them some resilience against external changes such as cocoa price fluctuations and disease.

The Ghanaian Government is currently planning how to incentivise adoption of cocoa agroforestry practices and support national extension activities in order that restoration activities are in “full alignment with the national REDD+ strategy, new Ghana Cocoa Sector Development Strategy II, and other relevant national strategies and plans” (IDH, 2018). In addition, a “multi-stakeholder landscape approach will form the basis for the interventions, with an initial focus on the six Climate-Smart Cocoa Hotspot Intervention Areas (HIAs) as defined under the Ghana Cocoa Forest REDD+ Program (GCFRP)” (IDH, 2018). Climate-Smart cocoa is essentially a cocoa agroforestry system, but with a particular focus on creating agricultural systems that reduce negatives impacts on and promote resilience to changes in our climate (IDH, 2018).

Within this context, Condatis could be useful in providing a method for strategically planning forest restoration activities within the cocoa sector, contributing to the conservation of biodiversity and to the creation of resilient landscapes.

This case study has focused on exploring the potential impact of cocoa shade expansion on wildlife connectivity between two protected areas within the Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve-Bia Hills National Park landscape, in the high-forest zone of Western Ghana (Fig. 1). Bia National Park (henceforth Bia), part of the Bia Biosphere Reserve, contains a core zone that is heavily protected and thus effectively provides an environment in which a wide variety of forest-dwelling fauna and flora can persist. The Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve (henceforth Krokosua) is a much more fragmented area, where production forest, in various stages of regrowth, is interspersed with semi-intact forest fragments and smallholder agriculture, encroaching from the edges. Though Krokosua does house a rich diversity of species, despite its more mixed land use, there is concern that that biodiversity is under threat from the ever-reducing habitat area and ever-increasing fragmentation and will thus need to move to Bia in order to seek refuge. Through understanding the spatial pattern by which threatened species might move through the landscape from Krokosua to Bia (Fig. 2), interventions can be made on the ground to improve the chances of that movement being successful, i.e. through strategically increasing the permeability of the landscape for migrating species. Condatis provides a way of mapping the spatial pattern of movement through landscapes in which the land cover, and its relative permeability for the species of interest, is defined.

Fig. 1 Ghana (delineated by the black line), with its Protected Area network highlighted in red and the Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve (to the east) and Bia National Park (to the west) outlined in yellow. (All maps were created in QGIS Version 2.18.18 and Bing Aerial used as the basemap, unless reported otherwise; the Protected Areas layer was downloaded from Protected Planet, protectedplanet.net/country/GH.)

One of the primary goals of this study, as outlined above, was to explore the inclusion of different social and economic parameters in the Condatis modelling, i.e. cost and stakeholder preference. A lack of data specific to this area and its resident farmers prevented the incorporation of these variables into the modelling. However, the current practices and attitudes of the local stakeholders, i.e. cocoa farmers, as identified through key informants, were considered in the development of the study as far as possible. This is reflected by the species of interest chosen for the Condatis analyses: two theoretical species of forest-associated invertebrates, which play a role in improving the yield of

cocoa (discussed further below). These species were chosen on the premise that, if sun cocoa farms are converted into shade cocoa farms through the planting of shade¹ trees, the landscape will become more permeable for these forest-dependent species, thus their populations will increase in the landscape at distance from Krokosua and cocoa yields will increase, incentivizing farmers to plant more shade trees and forest patches within their estate.

Based on the study's goals, the data available and on information gathered through a workshop with researchers within the Faculty of Renewable Natural Resources at the Kwame Nrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST) in April 2018, we defined the parameters of this Condatis case study (Table 1). Considering the parameters detailed in Table 1 is an important exercise to perform prior to running any analysis in Condatis and will improve the likelihood of an output proving useful.

Fig. 2 The Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve and Bia National Park in western Ghana, outlined in yellow and red, respectively. The map demonstrates how forest, which would have extended over much of the area shown in the past, does not reach the edges of Krokosua in some places. The lack of large patches of forest within the cocoa farming landscape in between the two protected areas is distinct, though there is a mosaic of sun and shade cocoa, small patches of forest, other agriculture and infrastructure within this landscape (as further demonstrated in Fig. 4). (The boundary of Krokosua and Bia were downloaded from Protected Planet, protectedplanet.net/country/GH.)

¹ Shade trees represent any species of tree that will reach a canopy height greater than that of cocoa, intercepting some sunlight, reducing the amount that reaches the cocoa trees whilst increasing the biodiversity of a cocoa farm. Shade trees can either be present due to natural growth or human planting, and often provide additional benefits to the farmer through the timber or fruits they provide.

Table 1 Key parameters for consideration when designing an analysis in Condatis, and the specific details of those defined for this case study. *Details of parameters described further in *Methods*.

<i>What kind of species are you interested in?</i>	Forest-associated species of moderate specialism (able to use shade cocoa). Habitat quality is defined by tree cover (TS1) or by overall species richness (TS2).
<i>What is your source and target?</i>	Source is Krokosua Hills ; target is Bia National Park
<i>Why do your species need to move between the focal source and target?</i>	Habitat fragmentation (and climate change)
<i>What constitutes habitat?</i>	Shade cocoa (<i>Cocoa + tree</i>) & forest (<i>Natural & Disturbed</i>)*
<i>What kind of prioritisation are you performing?</i>	Identification of key locations for restoration of cocoa agroforestry /expansion of shade cocoa
<i>Who will be interested in the results?</i>	National REDD+ Secretariat, Forestry Commission

III. Methods

A series of *flow* and *dropping* analyses were performed in Condatis, exploring the connectivity of the Krokosua Hills landscape for two theoretical invertebrate species associated with cocoa agroforestry habitats (Table 1). The *colonisation speed* of a landscape is a measure of how connected a landscape is for the species of interest (Hodgson *et al.*, 2012): a greater colonisation speed represents greater connectivity, i.e. the presence of a more connected habitat network. Prior to running the analyses, the input parameters were defined, and input raster layers generated.

(i) Species parameters

Two theoretical species were chosen on which to perform the Condatis analyses: Theoretical Species 1 (TS1) and Theoretical Species 2 (TS2), based on two forest-associated invertebrate species (able to use shade cocoa as habitat), commonly found within cocoa farming landscapes in west Africa (Table 2). As mentioned, these species were chosen as examples of species that would likely provide benefits to cocoa productivity if their population sizes increased within cocoa farms; such population increases would be expected to result from the planting of shade trees within cocoa farms, i.e. the extension of shade cocoa agriculture. The various parameters required for a Condatis analysis were estimated for these two species using information from the literature (Table 3). A generic reproductive rate of 1000 individuals per km² was chosen for each species in the absence of specific information, and three different dispersal distances were modelled: 0.2km, 0.5km and 1.0km, in order to assess whether changes in this parameter cause notable changes in movement patterns between the source and target.

Table 2 The parameters of the two theoretical species of interest, TS1 and TS2.

Description	Theoretical Species 1 (TS1)	Theoretical Species 2 (TS2)
Example species	<i>Dorylus wilverthi</i> (Driver ant)	<i>Oecophylla smaragdina</i> (Weaver ant)
Ecosystem function	nutrient cycling; “valuable pest control service” ¹	
Habitat preference	Forest cover >11% ²	Biodiversity richness

¹Schöning (2008)

²Peters *et al.* (2011)

Table 3 The parameters of the variables required to perform analyses in Condatis, populated with data for the two theoretical species, TS1 and TS2. Further information on the variables are provided in the text below.

Condatis variable	Definitions of parameter for TS1/TS2
Reproductive rate (RR) (individuals/km ²)	1000
Dispersal distance (DD) (km)	0.2, 0.5 & 1.0km travelled per individual per generation
Source/Target raster	Movement between the Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve (Source) & Bia National Park (Target)
Habitat raster	TS1 ~ canopy cover; TS2 ~ biodiversity richness
Restoration scenario (used in dropping analyses)	Sun cocoa → cocoa agroforestry

(ii) Raster layer parameters

The raster layers were prepared according to the parameters defined in Table 4. The cell resolution was set to 50m x 50m for the flow analyses and 100m x 100m for the dropping analyses, in order to reduce the cells within the landscape to a number that Condatis could easily run, i.e. less than 40,000 pixels. Since the original land cover map on which the raster layers were based, provided by David Hughell (Rainforest Alliance, 2014), consisted of pixels of spatial resolution 5m x 5m, an aggregation was performed to create habitat layers of these coarser resolutions.

Table 4 The parameters of all raster layers used in the Condatis analyses, i.e. Source/Target, Habitat rasters and those used to represent the Restoration scenarios.

Raster layers	Coordinate Reference System (CRS)	Cell resolution	North	East	South	West
Source/Target; Habitat	EPSG:25000	50m	45304.337890	217045.819314	66904.3378901	182195.819314
Restoration		100m	45422.2975163	217276.837458	66822.2975163	182576.837458

Source/Target

The source was chosen as the Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve and target as Bia National Park, to illustrate the scenario where movement of individuals may occur from a smaller, more fragmented and diminishing area of habitat to a larger, protected area of habitat, where more resources are available.

A buffer of 1km of source/target area was created along the edge of the landscape of interest (Fig. 3). Only *Forest* and *Disturbed Forest* grid cells within these source/target buffer zones were then selected to form the Source and Target cells (Fig. 4). All Source cells were then assigned a value of 1, and all Target cells 2, in order for Condatis to recognise the cells appropriately.

Fig. 3 The boundary of the landscape of interest (red), with the raster layer showing the *Source* (blue) and *Target* (yellow).

Habitat parameters

Habitat quality for each of the theoretical species was defined according to their reported or assumed association with different components of forest: TS1 with tree canopy cover (Peters *et al.*, 2011) and TS2 with plant species richness. Rainforest Alliance (2014) data, obtained from field surveys of a standard plot size, was used to define the land cover according to its quality of habitat for each theoretical species (Table 5, Fig. 5). The highest value of canopy cover/biodiversity richness was used to represent the greatest habitat quality, i.e. 1 or 100%, and all other values calculated as relative to that. Condatis recognises habitat quality values associated with raster pixels between 0 and 1, thus all values were calculated as decimals.

Fig. 4 The Rainforest Alliance land cover map (Rainforest Alliance, 2014), providing information on land cover for the area of interest. Land cover classes are demonstrated in the adjacent key.

For TS1, the literature suggested that *Dorylus wilverthi* requires forest canopy cover of >11%, thus the habitat layer was generated to only comprise those land cover classes that exceeded this

threshold by some margin, to account for potentially small patch sizes of forest within the cocoa farms, i.e. *Cocoa + trees*, *Disturbed forest* and *Natural forest* land cover categories that all had a canopy cover of 18% or more (Table 5). For TS2, each pixel within the habitat raster layer was assigned a value to represent its quality, even those pixels providing very low habitat value, e.g. *Developed* land cover at only 3% (Table 5).

Table 5 Habitat quality values for each land cover type for each theoretical species, based on reported values from Rainforest Alliance (2014) plot surveys in the landscape of interest: TS1 according to canopy cover, and TS2 according to biodiversity richness. Fig. 5 graphically illustrates the relationships shown in this table.

Land cover class	No. of plots surveyed	Canopy cover (average % per plot)	TS1 Habitat Quality	Biodiversity Richness (average per plot)	TS2 Habitat Quality
Natural forest	37	46%	0.96	103	1.00
Disturbed forest	26	48%	1.00	89	0.89
Cocoa + trees	47	18%	0.38	74	0.74
Cocoa	75	13%	0	65	0.65
Open	19	10%	0	33	0.33
Developed	3	1%	0	3	0.03

(A)

(B)

(C)

Fig. 5 The *Habitat Quality* layer for: **(A)** TS1, based on an association with canopy cover, and **(B)** TS2, based on an association with biodiversity richness. (Lighter greens represent lower habitat quality; darker greens represent higher, on a scale from 0 to 1. The landscape of interest is shown in red.) The numerical values associated with each land cover are plotted in **(C)**.

Restoration scenarios

For each theoretical species, a scenario was developed to illustrate a potential future land cover pattern where cocoa agroforestry (i.e. *Cocoa + Trees* according to Rainforest Alliance (2014)) has expanded onto all land that is currently under sun cocoa (i.e. *Cocoa*) within the landscape of interest. These layers, referred to as *Prioritisation* layers, were developed to be used as input layers for *dropping* analysis in Condatis, which enables the prioritisation of different habitat pixels according to their contribution to flow, under a potential future habitat configuration.

In the TS1 restoration scenario, all land that is currently under sun cocoa, as depicted by Rainforest Alliance (2014), is converted to cocoa agroforestry, with an associated change in the pixel value to illustrate the improvement in habitat quality: $0.27 \rightarrow 0.38$ (Table 5, Fig. 6A). Similarly, in generating the restoration scenario for TS2, all land that is currently under sun cocoa, as depicted by Rainforest Alliance (2014), is converted to cocoa agroforestry, with an associated change in the pixel value to illustrate the improvement in habitat quality: $0.65 \rightarrow 0.74$ (Table 5). However, in this latter scenario, because the habitat quality layer comprises values for each pixel irrespective of land cover, the *Prioritisation* layer only comprised the added habitat value of the conversion from sun to shade cocoa, i.e. 0.09 (Fig. 6B).

As mentioned previously, the prioritisation layers used in the dropping analyses, had a pixel size of 100m x 100m.

(A) TS1

(B) TS2

Fig. 6 The two *Prioritisation* layers generated to represent potential restoration scenarios for each theoretical species if all pixels containing sun cocoa were converted to shade cocoa, i.e. cocoa agroforestry. (These scenarios are meant as illustrative only and do not represent planned restoration scenarios.) (Lighter reds represent lower habitat quality; darker reds represent higher, on a scale from 0 to 0.38. The landscape of interest is outlined in red.)

IV. Condatis Results

Here are reported the main outputs from the Condatis analyses for each species. A Condatis analysis computes a *flow value per cell*. Flow is a measure assigned to each habitat cell that gives an indication of the relative number of individuals moving through that cell that will go on to colonise the target (strictly speaking, their descendants will colonise the target). The larger the flow value of a habitat cell, the more important that cell is for connectivity between the source and the target. Flow of individuals only occurs through habitat cells, defined by the uploaded habitat map.

Another output of Condatis is the *colonisation speed* of the landscape. This is a measure of overall or total flow, i.e. successful movement of a species/taxonomic group from the source to the target. The faster the speed, the shorter the time taken to reach the target (specifically for the first individual to arrive at any target cell, not necessarily colonisation of the whole target area or movement of the whole population). If the landscape configuration changes and/or the species being modelled changes, the speed will change. For example, if a species has a shorter dispersal distance, or produces fewer individuals per km² per generation, all movement through the landscape will be slower. Landscape configuration can also have a large impact on speed (see [Hodgson et al., 2016](#) for more information on this). Speed is a relative measure that can be compared across scenarios computed by Condatis. Thus, it is a useful output in this case study as it enables us to

compare the influence of different restoration scenarios on the colonisation speed of the landscape, i.e. changes in connectivity resulting from changes forest cover.

FLOW

Theoretical Species 1

The Condatis *flow* maps for the three different dispersal distances of 0.2km, 0.5km and 1.0km for TS1 show broadly similar trends (Figs. 8A, B and C, respectively). These outputs illustrate two key patterns: (i) the main routes of movement between Krokosua and Bia are via the forest and cocoa agroforestry landscapes within the southern part of the landscape, where the distance between the protected areas is smallest; (ii) with increasing dispersal distance of TS1, the habitat further to the north of the landscape provides more connectivity for individuals, where distances between Krokosua and Bia are larger.

Fig. 7 The colour scale illustrating the relative flow through each grid cell within the landscape. Cells with high flow, i.e. that are of the greatest importance for enabling individuals of the species of interest to move through the landscape, are shown in black, and cells with the lowest flow, and thus provide little connectivity between the source and the target, are shown in cream.

Theoretical Species 2

The Condatis *flow* maps for the three different dispersal distances of 0.2km, 0.5km and 1.0km for TS2 also show broadly similar trends (Figs. 9A, B and C, respectively). These outputs illustrate two key patterns, which differ from those observed for TS1: (i) developed areas, i.e. settlements, are not being used despite their minimal habitat value; (ii) the buffer zone around Krokosua appears to be important for connectivity.

(A) 0.2km

(B) 0.5km

(C) 1.0km

Fig. 8 Condatis flow maps for TS1 for three dispersal distances: (A) 0.2km, (B) 0.5km, and (C) 1.0km. (The colour scale is explained in Fig. 7. The landscape of interest is outlined in red. The Source/Target have been set as transparent; refer to Fig. 3 for their locations.)

(A) 0.2km

(B) 0.5km

(C) 1.0km

Fig. 9 Condatis flow maps for TS2 for three dispersal distances: (A) 0.2km, (B) 0.5km, and (C) 1.0km. (The colour scale is explained in Fig. 8. The landscape of interest is outlined in red. The Source/Target have been set as transparent; refer to Fig. 3 for their locations.)

Comparing flow

When exploring the colonisation speeds for the different theoretical species, i.e. the speed at which the landscape is crossed by individuals, from source to target, all values suggest that the landscape is highly connected, irrespective of dispersal distances (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10 The overall colonisation speeds, as computed by Condatis, taken for the theoretical species, TS1 (orange) and TS2 (green), to cross the landscape between Krokosua and Bia, according to the different dispersal distances: 0.2km, 0.5km and 1.0km.

DROPPING

Dropping is a method used for prioritising patches of habitat for restoration or protection, when there is a restricted map of feasible areas for these activities on the ground. The method shows how additional habitat cells can increase the colonisation speed across a landscape of existing habitat and can also be used to highlight areas of an existing network that cannot afford to be lost due their contribution to connectivity. In this case study, dropping enables the mapping of where converting sun cocoa into shade cocoa and restoring patches of forest within the agricultural landscape, could enhance the connectivity needed for movement of wildlife between the Krokosua Hills and Bia protected areas. During a dropping analysis in Condatis, the flow of individuals through the potential additional habitat cells between the chosen *source* and *target* is computed; the cells are then ranked according to their contribution to the speed of species' movement, and the lowest-ranking additional cells are 'dropped' from the landscape. This procedure is repeated multiple times until only the most important cells remain, which contribute the most to flow, and the *prioritisation* exercise is complete. There are two alternative methods for prioritising the cells in Condatis: via *flow-based* or *number-based* dropping. Flow-based dropping involves dropping an equal proportion

of flow in each stage of dropping, and number-based dropping involves dropping an equal number of cells in each stage. (Further information on the dropping process, including the options on the number of stages over which to drop cells, can be found on the Condatis [Help page](#).) The number-based output may be simpler for ranking the landscape into broad bands, but the flow-based output gives more detail in high-flow areas, as seen here in the Krokosua-Bia landscape, making it a more useful method when decisions are being made on which specific locations to, for example, focus limited funds for agricultural extension work with farming communities.

Theoretical Species 2

In this case study, a flow-based dropping analysis was performed for TS2, to demonstrate how one of the outputs from Condatis, i.e. the *dropping rank* map, can be used to guide restoration efforts on the ground. In particular for this exercise, the analysis demonstrates where increasing biodiversity within the landscape would have the greatest impact on connectivity for our species of interest. Those cells with a higher rank in the dropping process are more important for connectivity, i.e. carry greater flow, whilst those with a lower rank are dropped first.

The dropping rank map (Fig. 11) demonstrates that the highest priority cells for connectivity are found in the south of the landscape of interest, and along the border of Krokosua.

Fig. 11 The *dropping rank* output for TS2 with a dispersal distance of 1 km, produced through a flow-based dropping analysis (over 50 stages), performed in Condatis. (The other parameters used in this dropping analysis are detailed in Tables 3 and 4. The colour scale is shown.)

V. Discussion

The high flow results from this set of analyses demonstrate that the landscape of interest in this study, i.e. the area extending between the Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve and Bia National Park, is generally well connected for the theoretical species modelled here. For both species, with somewhat different habitat requirements, similar habitat patches appear to be important for enabling connectivity (darker areas in Figs 8 and 9), and these are unaffected by the distances we assume individuals can disperse. This is an important finding because it indicates results are robust to the considerable uncertainty that exists about how real species will respond to this landscape. However, the northern part of the landscape becomes more important for connectivity as the dispersal distance increases, suggesting that larger, and or more widely dispersing species may use this area more for traversing between the two protected areas; thus this region must not be neglected by agricultural extension programmes. As perhaps expected, the developed areas provide minimal, if any opportunities for movement for our theoretical species. On the other hand, the zones directly adjacent to the protected areas, often called *Buffer Zones* in conservation science and management, are important and thus efforts to enhance and protect these as distinct zones, e.g. through converting sun cocoa to cocoa agroforestry farms, could contribute to improving the connectivity of the landscape. A buffer zone of sorts is already established around the core zone of Bia National Park, where more sustainable landscape management is being practiced.

The results from the dropping analysis performed suggest that increasing biodiversity richness, through restoring cocoa agroforestry in this case, could be beneficial over large portions of this landscape, but particularly so in the south and in 'buffer zones' at the edge of each protected area. If a choice was to be made, the southern part of the landscape could be the priority zone in which to invest agricultural extension funds and other forms of activity that promote cocoa agroforestry with resident farmers.

VI. Policy Relevance

The outputs from this set of Condatis analyses could contribute to developing a national map for Ghana on where to prioritise cocoa agroforestry extension activities: Condatis' dropping function could facilitate the inclusion of "mapping of exact areas to intensify establishment of shaded cocoa landscapes in line with the Ghana Cocoa Forest REDD+ Programme (GCFRP) (20 year programme)" (World Cocoa Foundation, 2017). Through focusing on the most ecologically efficient areas for enhancing the movement of key species across the expanse of cocoa farms, Condatis outputs could help to improve the success and reduce the overall cost of creating more resilient cocoa production landscapes in Ghana.

This report has not discussed some of the current barriers to changing cocoa farming practices on the ground. These include, though are not limited to: issues of land and tree tenure (though reform to legislation has been declared under the Joint Framework for Action (IDH, 2018)); working with and within the Community Resource Management (CREMA) structure of rural organisation; and lacking clear scientific evidence of the multiple and specific benefits of planting shade trees within cocoa farms. For example, it is important to gather data on the yield enhancements of shade cocoa systems over sun cocoa, over the full cycle of the crop, i.e. 25 years. Once this information is available, translated into accessible forms and clear management options, there will be more opportunities for NGOs and other organisations to facilitate knowledge exchange with stakeholders on the ground. There are a variety of different NGOs, for example SNV, Rainforest Alliance and

Conservation Alliance, which are working in Ghana to promote cocoa agroforestry as a means of enhancing the conservation and sustainable management of forest resources, the latter two of which are working in the Bia-Krokosua landscape, e.g. [Bia Conservation Area Project](#).

VII. Limitations

This study was performed to illustrate the outputs that Condatis is capable of producing for a variety of landscapes. We were particularly interested in exploring how two different species experienced different connectivity because of different relative habitat suitability. While this has been achieved, the landscape and scenarios of this case study do not fit Condatis' assumptions in some ways: principally, the wildlife corridor is only approximately 15km at its widest stretch, so crossing it does not necessitate multi-generational dispersal for species with longer dispersal distances, such as amphibians and birds, for which there was interest in modelling at the inception of this case study.

Another limitation of this study was that theoretical species, rather than actual species and their parameters, were used on which to model multi-generational movement across the landscape. Therefore, outputs were only indicative of potential species movement patterns, and the modelling implicitly assumes that *species need to move between the focal source and target* (Table 1). was merely an illustration of what *may* be of interest to stakeholders on the ground.

This Condatis case study was also hindered by a lack of data on the ecology of cocoa farming landscapes, and the species that they share with adjacent forests; an important data gap to address given the importance of the cocoa industry in regions that also hold unique and threatened biodiversity. With more temporally resolved habitat suitability data for the variety of different species of conservation interest, and within larger landscapes of interest across the cocoa-producing regions of the country (in which the expansion of cocoa agroforestry is feasible), Condatis could provide more informative maps of use in the building of resilience and long-term sustainable management of cocoa farming in Ghana. Furthermore, if spatial socio-economic data were available to infer some of the costs and benefits of future land use/management changes, Condatis prioritisation could potentially find solutions that will be more practical to implement, by not conflicting with other policy and local livelihood priorities.

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IX. References

- Hodgson, J.A., Thomas, C.D., Dytham, C., Travis, J.M.J., and Cornell, S.J. (2012) The Speed of Range Shifts in Fragmented Landscapes. *PLOS ONE*, 7(10): e47141. doi:[10.1371/journal.pone.0047141](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0047141).
- Hodgson, J.A., Wallis, D.W., Krishna, R., and Cornell, S.J. (2016) How to manipulate landscapes to improve the potential for range expansion. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 7: 1558-1566. doi:[10.1111/2041-210X.12614](https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12614).

IDH (2018) *Cocoa and Forests Initiative - Joint Framework for Action, Ghana*. Available from url: <https://www.idhsustainabletrade.com/uploaded/2017/11/Ghana-Framework-Final-082418.pdf>. Accessed on 06/02/2019.

Peters, M. K., Lung, T. , Schaab, G. and Wägele, J. (2011) Deforestation and the population decline of the army ant *Dorylus wilverthi* in western Kenya over the last century. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 48: 697-705. doi:[10.1111/j.1365-2664.2011.01959.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2011.01959.x).

Protected Planet (2018) *Ghana, Africa*. Available from url: <https://www.protectedplanet.net/country/GH>. Accessed in March 2018.

Rainforest Alliance (2014). *Nature Ecosystem Assessment Baseline for Ghana and Indonesia*. Evaluation and Research Program, Rainforest Alliance.

Ruf, F.O. (2011) The Myth of Complex Cocoa Agroforests: The Case of Ghana. *Human Ecology*, 39(3): 373-388.

Schöning, C. (2008) Driver Ants (*Dorylus* subgenus *Anomma*) (*Hymenoptera: Formicidae*). In: Capinera J.L. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Entomology*. Springer, Dordrecht

Wessel, M. and Quist-Wessel, P.M.F. (2015) Cocoa production in West Africa, a review and analysis of recent developments. *NJAS - Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences*, 74–75: 1-7.

World Cocoa Foundation (2017) *Climate Smart Cocoa – An Introduction to the CSC Program*. Available from url: https://www.idhsustainabletrade.com/uploaded/2017/06/WCF-CSC_1RT-Cocoa-and-Forests-Initiative.pdf. Accessed on 06/02/2019.